

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 –2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<https://arseam.com/content/vol1-issue-01-may-2014>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Email: editor@arseam.com

THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF URDU ESSAYS OF SYED HASAN ASKARI

Md. Shamim

Research Scholar, Department of Urdu
BhimRao Ambedkar Bihar University, Muzaffarpur

Abstract

A well-known authority on Medieval Indian History, Syed Hasan Askari was a renowned scholar and a prolific writer. He is widely known for his contributions in the area of medieval Indian history and most of his writings have been in English, however, he has also extensively written essays and research articles in Urdu language that have received appreciation from Urdu critiques, Scholars and readers. These essays cover a number of significant areas such as Manuscripts in Bihar, Malik Mohammad Jaisi, Manuscripts of Deccani Urdu, Diwan of Syed Raja, Ujagar Chnad Ulfat, Chandayan, Tarikh e Kashmir, Contribution of Muslims in Hindi Literature, Urdu-Hindi Languages, Sufism of Northern India, Sikh-Muslim Relations during Mughal Period etc. A closer look at these essays reveals that Syed Hasan Askari has made significant contribution in promotion of Urdu Language and Literature and had a good knowledge of Persian and Arabic Languages. This Research Paper is an attempt to highlight his contributions as Urdu Essay writer.

Key words: Syed Hasan Askari, Urdu Essays, Bihar, Medieval Indian History

Introduction

Syed Hasan Askari, son of late Syed Razi Hasan was born in 1901 in his ancestral home in Khujwa in Siwan district. He belonged to a middle class educated family, and received his traditional education at home. He passed the matriculation examination from Chapra high school in 1918 securing a first division and the district junior scholarship and graduate from the then

G.B.B. College (now L.S. College) in 1922. He did his post-graduation in history and LLB from Patna University in 1924 and 1925 respectively. He joined the teaching profession in 1926 and worked as a lecturer and professor of History, Patna College. He got an opportunity be in this distinguished service for nearly 40 years and was deeply involved in academic and research work. He was also associated with many reputed institutes and organization such as K P Jaiswal research Institute Patana, Indian Historical Records Commission, Indian History Congress, Regional Records Service Commission, India Gazetteer, Khuda Bakhsh Khan Oriental Library and others. Thus he spent most of his lifespan in research work making significant contributions in the fields of history, numismatics, paleography, art, culture and literature. He is credited with the reconstruction of the political history of medieval Bihar and is also known for writing history of Sufism in Bihar besides his substantial contribution to the social history of Bihar in general.

Highlighting the contributions of Syed Hasan Askari, Prof Imtiyaz Ahmad , former Director of Khuda Bakhsh Khan Library writes:

“Syed Hasan Askari was one of the most distinguished representatives of the Bihar School of Medievalists. He blazed a trail in historical research and writing, bringing to light many unknown historical sources and introducing these to the academic world in general, and to the scholars and researches working on the medieval India and Bihar, in particular. He unravelled new facts and provided new information that enriched the understanding of various facts of the history of medieval Bihar and India-political, social, religious and cultural. For well over half a century, he strode like a colossus in the academic circles of the state, bequeathed a rich legacy of historical writings and inspired several generations of scholars and researchers. He was one of those rare persons who represent an institution in themselves.”

Urdu Essays and Research Papers of Syed Hasan Askari

Among major contributions of Syed Hasan Askari are his scholarly articles, essays and research papers published in various newspapers, magazines and journals of repute. These essays and research papers were written mostly in English, however, a good number of these were also written in Urdu. According to Prof Syed Hasnain the number of essays/research papers published by Syed Hasan Askari is about 250 while Prof Anwarul Haqie Tabassum has suggested this figure to be around 350. Prof Imtiyaz Ahmad has provided a list of 44 essays/research papers that were published in Urdu. The list is as follows:

1. Nuskha e Dilkusha
2. Nuskha e Mufeed ul Insha
3. Jung Nama
4. Tareekh e Kashmir
5. Zafar Nama e Almgiri
6. Nuskha-e-Khulasatut Ansaab
7. Gharib ka Urdu Kalaam
8. Shamali Hindustan ke Sufiae Karaam ki Hindi Dosti
9. Jaisi aur chand Musalmaan Hindu Shora ke kalaam ka ek Hindi Nuskha
10. Diwaan e Syed Raja
11. Deccani Urdu Makhtootaat per ek Nazar
12. Urdu Hindi Zabanein
13. Auraq e Paarina
14. Wali Vellorawi
15. Syed Abdul Quddoos Gangohi aur aur unka Hindi Kalaam
16. Chandayan Mulla Dawood aur Minast
17. Hindi Funon e Latifa aur Chandayin ki chand Tasweerein
18. Masnawi Gauhar Jauhri Urdu
19. Awwalin Musلمان aur Desi Bhashayein
20. Suba e Bihar ke Aakhri Governor
21. Sandesh Rask Ek Musلمان ki apbhranshai Hindi mein ek Manzoom kitab
22. Quroon e Wusta ke Bihar mein Tasawwuf
23. Bihar Shareif mein Qalmi Nuskhon ke Zakhirey
24. Bahadur Shah Rangoon Mein
25. Dastur e Mulla Firoz
26. Kuchh Hazrat Makhдум ke Malafiz o Makateeb ke Muta'alliq
27. Afsana e Badshahan
28. Key Kard ke Na Yaft
29. Ilmut Tarekh
30. Hazrat Hesamuddin
31. Gajn Faiyaazi
32. Sikh Mughal Ta'alluqat
33. Istidrak bar Nuskha e Mufid ul Insha
34. Ujagar CHnad Ulfat ka Urdu Kalaam
35. Ujagar Chnad ulfat aur unki Nadir

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| Ghair matbua Tasaneef | 40. Kuchh Hashr se Muta'aliq |
| 36. Zainudin ki Tabqat e Babari | 41. Hussaini Mian Zareef |
| 37. Do Makhtoote | 42. Sitara e Baadban |
| 38. Diwaan e Nak Shah Auragabadi | 43. Qazi Sahab: Alim aur Insaan and |
| 39. Lala CHnad Ujagar CHnad Ulfat | 44. Professor Mehfuzul Haque |

The abovementioned writings of Syed Hasan Askari broadly covers the topics related to Medieval Indian History, Persian Manuscripts, Sufism, Culture, Religion and Language. Most of these essays, research papers and articles were published in reputed journals and newspapers such as Maasir, Patna University Journal, Nadeem, Motalaa, Saghar, Hayaat e Kaleem, Aurang and Sadaa e Aam. Most publications found place in a journal called Maasir that used to be published from Patna. Dr. Azeemuddin Ahmad was the first editor of this Urdu journal that was launched in the year 1940. It is pertinent to mention that the five major objectives of publication of this journal were described by the publishers as follows:

- (1) Publication of standard Urdu critical essays
- (2) Publication of standard Urdu research articles
- (3) Publication of unpublished important manuscripts of Urdu
- (4) Discussion and analysis on various scientific and literary issues of Urdu
- (5) Publication of such articles of Urdu that are related to social, cultural and religious issues.

The above objectives were certainly incorporated in all the articles and essays written by Syed Hasan Askari. It is also important to note that his writings were not only relevant in terms of historical significance but also in terms of its evaluation as a literary work of Urdu. Had it not been relevant for Urdu Literature, it would probably not have found a place in magazines such as Maasir. As we delve deeper into the writings, we also realize that he could not only write in Urdu language but was also well versed in Persian. He frequently quotes Classical Persian Texts such as Jawame ul Hekayaat , Diwaan e Hafiz, Akhbarul Akhyar, Siratul Auliya and others.

Hasan Askari has touched upon a variety of subjects in his Urdu essays and has done justice to all his selected subjects. Be it the interpretation and edition of a rare manuscript or describing a historical event or analysing work of Indian Poets or mysticism, he seems to have equal

command over all the subjects. His writings reflect upon his scholarship and multi-disciplinary approach.

Some Popular Urdu Essays of Hasan Askari and their themes

As mentioned earlier, around 45 essays and research articles have been listed as part of his Urdu writings. Since Syed Hasan Askari was a historian, it is needless to mention that his writings on the area of history and society are of great relevance. One such article is Ilmut Tareekh (علم التاريخ) that was published in the journal Masir in 1983. This article deals with issues related to history such as meaning and definition of history, history writing in Persian and Arabic, essential components of history writing etc. "Awwaleen Musalman aur Desi Bhashaayein" (اولین مسلمان) (اور دیشی بھاشائیں) . This research article was published in Patna University Journal in 1955. He describes the contributions of Masood Saad Salman and Amir Khusro, Hazrat Ganj Shakar, Hazrat Bakhtar Kaki, Hazrat Nizamuddin Aulia and others.

Another significant essay of Hasan Askari is "Urdu Hindi Zabanein (اردو ہندی زبانیں)" wherein he throws light upon origin and development of these two languages. He has also touched upon the controversies related to these languages and also issues related to the script of Urdu language. One of his essays entitled "Hazrat Abdul Quddus Gangohi aur Unka Hindi Kalaam (حضرت عبد القدوس گنگوہی اور انکا ہندی کلام)" was published in the journal Masir in 1957, wherein, besides describing the merits of Hindawi kalaam of Abdul Quddus Gangohi, he also discusses in detail, issues related to Sufism have also been discussed. Origin and development of Chishti Order, its founders and other major Sufis of this Order have been described in this essay. Sheikh Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri was among the most prominent Sufis of Bihar and his Maktoobat and Malfuzat are of great literary importance. Syed Hasan wrote an article entitled "Kuchh Hazrat Makhdum ke Malafiz o Makateeb ke Muta'alliq (کچھ حضرت مخدوم بہار ملافیظ و مکاتیب کے متعلق)" . In this article he elaborates upon the literary and historical significance of the letters and anecdotes of Sheikh Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri.

Thus, Prof Syed Hasan Askari has extensively written in Urdu and has received appreciation from the critiques of Urdu Literature. Prof Kalimuddin Ahmad remembers him as "symbol of research" and says research was everything for him and added that Syed Hasan Askari spent all his life in pursuit of research. Commenting upon his Urdu writings Kalimuddin Ahmad says that

Hasan Askari used write everything in detail without taking any short-cuts. This led his sentences to be long and sometimes complex. It is interesting to note that he used to make corrections until the last moments of publication, which at times was troublesome for calligraphers and typists to compose his articles. Other critiques and contemporaries such as Mr. Abid Raza Bedar, Dr. Iqbal Hussain , Prof Imtiyaz Ahmad, Prof Syed Hasnain and Prof Khaliq Ahmad Nizami have also appreciated the Urdu writings of Syed Hasan Askari

References:

- Ejaz Ali Arshad , Bihar ki Bahaar Azimabaad Bisween Sadi Mein, Patna,
- Khuda Bakhsh Library Journal Vol. 140, Patna
- Mirza Khalil Ahmad Baig, Urdu Zaban Ki Tarikh , Educational Publishing House New Delhi,
- R R Diwakar, Bihar through Ages, Kashi Prasad Research Institute, Patna
- Syed Hasan Askari, Islam and Muslims in Bihar, Khuda Bakhsh Oriental Library, Patna, 1998
- Syed Hasan Askari, Masir, Vol 3, Patna 1952.
- S A Sher, Contribution of Bihar to Arabic Persian and Islamic Learning, IOPSRAP, Patna
- Zaban o Adab, Quarterly Journal, P 39-40, March 1982, Patna